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We hereby acknowledge receipt of your request for grant of a European patent as follows:

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Date of receipt	17 October 2025	
Your reference	P1736.8 EP	
Applicant	UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	
Country	PT	
Title	SKIN MODEL FOR SYNCHRONIZING STUDIES OF PERMEATION AND MEMBRANE INTERACTIONS	
Documents submitted	package-data.xml application-body.xml ARCHIVE.zip\P1736.8 EP 2025.10.17 - FILE.zip f1002-1.pdf (1 p.)	ep-request.xml ep-request.pdf (5 p.) SPECEPO-1.pdfP1736.8 EP 2025.10.17 - FILE.pdf (48 p.)
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